

Impact of COVID-19 on online shopping- A study with special reference to Belthangady Taluk

Pavana

Lecturer in Commerce

University College

Nellyadi.

Article Link: <https://aksharasurya.com/2024/03/pavana.php>

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10775024>

ABSTRACT:

The corona virus (COVID-19) pandemic is first and prime human tragedy across the globe, affecting the lives of millions of people. It has greatly impacted the global economy. The worldwide spread of the COVID-19 pandemic has disrupted how people buy products and services and how they perceive e-commerce. The standardized lockdown rules across India and the growing hesitation among consumers to go outside and shop for essential goods have tilted the nation towards e-commerce. With the emergence of globalization and digitization, people, places, and products have started coming close, approachable as well as affordable. Life was very fast, as everything from toilet roll to airplane ticket was just one click away. All the business plans, meetings, trips came to halt with the introduction of COVID-19 to the globe. The situation of the COVID-19 outbreak, made people think, dynamically and timely diagnosis of how families have adjusted their spending and online shopping, and what are the characteristics of the households who have responded the fastest and strongest. This study is an attempt to see the impact of COVID-19 on buying behaviour of consumers through online shopping -with Special reference to Belthangady Taluk.

KEYWORDS:

COVID -19, online shopping, e-commerce.

.....

INTRODUCTION

Online shopping is a method of buying products through electronic devices such as mobile or computers by using internet. People mostly prefer buying products by going physically in markets rather than buying online it is because of various reasons and the prominent reason from them is concerns of quality of products that people buy online this is what insist them buying physical. Although there are several advantages of online shopping like less expensive, time saving etc. But they are quality conscious. The world is facing one of the worst disasters in the history. As the world is in the devastating situation and countries have been put under lockdown, restrictions have been imposed on going out of homes, arranging crowded events, going in markets, almost every business has been shut down in the world in the wake of COVID-19 and people are stressed to stay in homes. Prior to the Covid-19 epidemic, traditional enterprise retailers were focused on driving growth, and acquiring market share with physical stores as their epicentre. Increasing traffic to their online store was not a major focus and took a backseat compared to driving footfalls to their physical stores.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To assess the impact of Covid -19 pandemic on online shopping

2. To evaluate the reasons for increased dependence of consumers on online shopping.
3. To suggest some measures for online shopping sites to improve their services.

METHODOLOGY:

The study is analytical in nature. For the purpose of study both primary data and secondary data has been collected. The convenience sampling method is used to collect primary data by taking respondents from rural area of Belthangady taluk. 50 respondents were considered for the study. Secondary data is from the published research papers, books and from websites.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY:

1. The sample size is limited only to 50 respondents.
2. Time was limited to conduct a detail stud

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

Table No 1 : Age

Age	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
Less than 25 years	24	48
25-35 years	9	18
35-45 years	8	15
45 years and above	9	18
Total	50	100

The above table shows the age category of respondents. 48% of respondents belongs to less than 25 years age category 18% belongs to 25-35 years, 15% belongs to 35-45 years and 18% belongs to 45 years and above age category.

Table No 2 : Educational level of respondents

Educational level of respondents	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
Primary	2	4
High school	3	6
Graduation	7	14
Post graduation	38	76
Total	50	100

The above table states the educational qualification of respondents. Majority of respondents i.e. 76% are of postgraduates, 14% are graduates and 6% are of high school and 4% are holding primary educational qualification. From the above table it is clear that the educated people are doing more and more online shopping.

Table No 3: Monthly income

Monthly income	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
Less than 20000	33	66
20000-40000	9	18
40000-60000	3	6
60000 and above	5	10
Total	50	100

The above table shows monthly income of respondents. 66% of respondents are having the income less than 20000, 18% are having income ranging in between 20000-40000, 6% respondents are having income in between 40000-60000 and 10% are having income 60000 and above.

Table No 4: Access of the internet services

Frequently access the internet?	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
Home	40	80
College	9	18
Cyber	1	2
Total	50	100

The above table shows the access of the internet services by the respondents. 80% of the respondents are accessing internet at home 18% of respondents are using internet services at college and the least i.e 2% are accessing internet at cyber.

Table No 5: Awareness about online shopping

Awareness about online shopping	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
By friends	17	34
By family	9	18
Through advertisements	20	40
By fellow worker	4	8
Total	50	100

The above table shows the awareness of online shopping to the respondents. Majority of the respondent's i.e 40% of them are came to know about online shopping through advertisements. 34% of them are aware about online shopping through their friends 18% of them are through family members and 8% of them are came to know from their fellow workers. From the above data it is clear that advertisement can be used to create awareness about online shopping.

Table No 6: Commodities purchased through online shopping

Number of respondents	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
Groceries	16	20
Clothes	23	30
Electronic gadgets	14	18
Books	10	12
Any other	16	20
Total	79	100

MRR:1.58

The above table shows the commodities purchased by the respondents through online shopping during covid period. Majority of the respondents did online shopping for clothes i.e 30%, 20% of them purchased groceries, 18% of them are purchased electronic gadgets and 12% of them are purchased books and 20% of them are purchased other commodities like cosmetics, bed sheets from online shopping.

Table No 7: Amount spent on online purchase during COVID period

Approximate amount	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
Less than 1000	13	26
1000-5000	25	50
5000-15000	5	10
More than 15000	7	14
Total	50	100

The above table shows the amount spent on online shopping during covid period. Majority of respondents spent 1000-5000 to online shopping i.e 50%, 26% of them are spent less than 1000, 14% are spent more than 15000 and 10% of them are spent 5000-15000 amount on online shopping.

Table No.8: Apps used for the purpose of online shopping

Applications	Number of re-spondents	Percentage of respondents
Amazon	35	34
Flip kart	35	34
Snap deal	4	4
OLX	3	3
Myntra	13	12
eBay	1	1
other	13	12
Total	104	100

MRR: 2.08

The above table shows the different apps used by the respondents for online shopping during Covid period. Most of the respondents preferred Amazon and Flip kart app for their online shopping i.e 34% 12% of them are preferred Myntra, 4%are preferred snap deal, 3%preferred OLX and1% are preferred Ebay and 12% are preferred other apps like jio mart, Ajio etc for their online shopping. From the data it is clear that most of the people preferring Amazon and Flip Kart apps for their online shopping.

Table No 09 : Reasons for online shopping during covid period

preference	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
It saves time	15	30
It is safe to shop at any time of the day	23	46
Products available on the internet is broad	10	20
It reduces the non tax cost of traditional shopping	2	4
Total	50	100

The above table shows the reasons for online shopping during covid period. 46% of the respondents opined that it is safe to shop at any time of the day, 30% revealed that it saves time, 20% opined that products available on the internet is broad, and 4% revealed that it reduces non tax cost of traditional shopping.

Table No.10: Specification of problem

Problems	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
Delay in delivery	8	32
Cheaper quality	10	40
Damaged products	3	12
Non delivery of product	4	16
Total	25	100

MRR: 1.31**IMPACT FACTOR (RPRI): 4.8**

The above table shows the problems faced by the respondents. 40% stated that cheaper quality of products are delivered to customers, 32% stated that there is delay in delivery, 12% stated that damaged products were delivered and 16% revealed that they didn't received their items ordered through online shopping.

Table No. 11: Features necessary for an online shopping site

Necessary features	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
Multiple payment gateways	8	16
Social networking integration	4	8
Privacy & security check out	20	40
Design	8	16
Customer friendly	10	10
Total	50	100

The above table shows the respondents opinion towards features that is necessary for online shopping site. 40% stated that privacy and security checkout is necessary in online shopping, 20%specified that these online shopping sites should be customer friendly, 16% opined that multiple payment gateways and more and more designs required and 8% stated that social networking integration is required on the part of online shopping sites.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- » 76% of online shoppers are of postgraduates. It shows that educated people are showing more and more interest in on-line shopping.
- » 80% of the respondents are accessing internet at home. It is clear that during their leisure time people will online shopping sites in order to place order for the commodities.
- » 40% of them are come to know about online shopping through advertisements. From the above data it is clear that advertisement can be used to create awareness about online shopping.
- » Majority of the respondents did online shopping for clothes i.e 30%.as female respondents are more in number there is more demand for dress materials in online shopping.
- » The study clearly indicates that most of the people preferring Amazon and Flip Kart apps for their online shopping
- » 46% of the respondents opined that it is safe to shop at any time of the day. From the safety point of majority were opted for online shopping during covid period
- » From the study it is clear that products available over the online shopping sites are of cheaper quality.
- » Majority i.e 40% stated that privacy and security checkout is necessary in online shopping sites.

SUGGESTIONS

1. As more and more number of people opted online shop-

- ping for their basic necessary goods, online shopping sites should improve the quality of products to retain their consumers for a longer period of time
2. Online shopping sites should give priority for privacy and security checkout so that consumers feel safe to purchase products from internet services.
 3. Companies can use advertisements as a weapon to popularise their online shopping sites.

CONCLUSIONS

Compared to shopping pre-pandemic, online shoppers have all boosted their online buying behaviours since the corona virus outbreak began. While “total cost” is initially the top factor in deciding whether to buy from one company over another, “previous positive experience” is the number one cited factor in deciding to return to make a purchase on a website or mobile app. In instances where customers report a negative online experience, large majorities find it important that the company follow up with the resolution in deciding if they will make a purchase from that company in the future.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. <https://www.getfeedback.com/resources/cx/the-pandemics-impact-on-the-state-of-online-shopping-worldwide/>
2. <https://www.bakertilly.com/insights/importance-e-commerce-post-pandemic-world>